

‘Our pasts, their past’:

Cultural heritage, popular domain and archaeology in Bangladesh

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These days, we, the urban middle class people, are very familiar with the notion of ‘safeguarding our heritage’. The credit of this ‘awareness’ goes principally to growing media representation of sensitizing archaeological discoveries and of destruction of cultural heritage or recovery of smuggled antiquities by the law enforcing agencies. This is a new phenomenon in Bangladesh urban sphere. The rise and development of the new intensity and formation of a new found desire in the metropolitan urban space can be temporally bound within the last decade or so, that saw differential changes and shifts in the consumerism, outburst of media and communication network. A different version of cultural heritage is being produced in contemporary Bangladesh. It is different than the previous one. It has a very different aura and attraction, particularly to the elite consumer middle class. It is a brand. A commodity. A product on which intellectual and financial investments can be made. A product that can be consumed, and more importantly, the consumption transforms the identity of the consumer. Here, I am talking strictly about the archaeological aspects of heritage, although these arguments are viable for non-archaeological aspects of heritage, also. In academic and institutional terminology, the former type of heritage is categorized as ‘Tangible Heritage.’

During the last decade or so, various non-governmental institutions and organizations have been established to work on cultural heritage in Bangladesh. I may cite several examples that overtly manifest the growing and shifting impact of ‘Heritage’ on particular sectors in metropolitan space. I refer to those examples later. Before doing that, I think I must elaborate on some interesting aspects of heritage from the recent discussions and debates on around the world.

There is intimate connection between heritage, past and identity. In recent archaeological literature, these connections are analyzed and substantiated from various perspectives. Considering the space and context, it wouldn’t be necessary to go into the details of those overtly theoretical issues. These connections are represented through various assumptions that we think as normal, as established, as emancipatory. Let me summarize those simply:

First, the past can be read, reconstructed and circulated through archaeological remains that are identified as ‘Heritage’ (a more common term is now cultural resource in the US). The heritage is local and global at the same time. The heritage is essential for the identity of a ‘nation’ and ‘ethnic groups’ in the sense that the root of a collectives (as nation or ethnic group) can be traced back, reconstructed and interpreted through archaeological works on ‘heritage’. The heritage, it is stated and circulated over and over again, helps us to know and reconstruct the past glory, pride and all the good recognition

of a nation. The glorious and prosperous past of a nation is essential for building a better national future. At the same time, heritage is perceived as the entangled to the identity of universal humankind, as it endorses the history of the human race.

Secondly, heritage can be protected and preserved. It is our sacred duty to protect heritage for the posterity, for the present study. We can protect our heritage. We must protect our heritage. The opposite is regarded as anti-national, anti-state, inhuman, and uncivilized. The desire and action to protect heritage thus becomes a standard as well as process to become a true citizen and patriot. Without the apparent expressions for the protection of heritage someone could easily be labeled as 'unconscious' and 'ignorant' of her/his civilized self identity.

Thirdly and most interestingly, the norms and processes of protection and the codes of conduct for preservation now codified as a systematic management system. Heritage must be managed. Fixing the terms and conditions of the management must be under sole authority of some institutions (such as, state and transnational agencies like UNESCO, ICOMOS, etc. and some experts. In the heritage vocabulary the authority of the institutions and specialist is popularly known as 'stewardship'. In US and West European countries Cultural Resource Management (CRM) has turned into an established discipline and institutional practice. State legal and juridical system has endorsed this particular aspect of stewardship. Renowned universities are offering degrees on CRM.

Fourthly and finally, heritage turns into an industry. A field where both financial and intellectual investments are made and profit is sought. Branding is done with nationalist aura. Selective symbols from the past are commodified and consumed within an exoticized marketing policy. Tourism and sustainable development, in this way, become enmeshed in the neo-liberal economy. Past is manufactured, sold and appropriated in many different ways and means. Objects and monuments connected to the memories of distress, pain and suffering, such as Nazi concentration camp like Auschwitz, turns into an object of modern touristic gaze. Scraps and rubbish from the Twin Towers in New York are transformed into replicas, and sold and consumed as a metaphor of loss and tears, as well as, as a validating artifact of United States imperial policy over the globe. Tajmahal is transformed into replicas and consumed in thousands in the celebration of immemorial love. As if, the consumption would reproduce the past at the present.

Heritage, it could be understood through its essential manifestations in our modern living, are embedded into our existence. In celebration of our joy. In memorizing our pain and distress. In manifesting our love and loyalty for country. In circulating the nationalist pride. In representing our ethnic supremacy and others' ethnic inferiority. In validating war on terror and killing millions. In legitimizing religious dictums, and so on. However, what is most crucial to point is that the heritage has profound political implications. By embedding deep into the memories, by manufacturing and consuming in the global market, and by making it an essential tool to construct identities, heritage often validate dominance and repression. Simultaneously, heritage may symbolize and mobilize resistance. It depends upon what heritage means in the relationship of the powerful and the weak.

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It is clear by now that heritage is not as simple as it seems. It is not only something from the past. It is enmeshed into our present. The meaning of the same heritage can be very different to people who views it, who perceives it. The most fundamental question that is raised by the activists of indigenous right groups from CRM sector: Who owns the past? In the United States, remains from the burials of the indigenous groups were perceived normally as objects of heritage and objects for the scientific study of the past. The objects of heritage thus were appropriated into a grand American National Identity. The history of the colonization of the land what was named as America was not so important to the specialists. The ethnic genocide committed by the Europeans in a not so distant past was out of focus in the scientific study of the past and objects. The projects were being launched in the name of the search for a multiple and flexible American identity In the early 90s, archaeologists, and indigenous right activists begun to raise their voice in terms of ownership. They proclaimed that the relics and human remains from hundreds of burials were part and parcel of the identity and history of the indigenous groups. These remains can not be owned either by some community of experts, scientists and archaeologists, or by the white Americans. The object and skeletal remains have deeply implicated religious significance that is intimately linked to the identity of the groups they belong. Various groups from the indigenous groups endorsed this position and claimed – ‘We own our past’ and started concerted mobilizations and protests against the very process of the study, manipulation and exoticization of the identity by the experts and the state. In the mid-90s, as an outcome of the protests, Native American Grave Protection Acts (NAGPRA) was enacted. In Australia, parallel and similar, resistance movements have given rise to the amendments of the existing laws and regulations pertaining to archaeological heritage. A set of code of conduct for the archaeologists and CRM managers have been formed.

These events have brought the issue of democracy of heritage. From another perspective, the movements of indigenous groups in America and Australia were for democratizing the heritage, established rights of the dominated and less privileged groups on their pasts. It was also about emancipating the past from the monopoly of a few experts.

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Most of readers know the archaeological site of Mahasthan, which has been identified as the ancient capital of Pundranagar. The sites history is under close scrutiny of the historians and archaeologists from colonial period. Archaeological excavations have been conducted and the history of the place is being written and revised over and over again. These histories are written by the experts. Yet, the experience of the past and the history is different in many ways to the commons in the area. The oral narratives by the local people narrate the histories in the ways that are completely opposite to the established historical narratives on the site. A mythical Hindu king Parashuram and a Muslim *peer* Shah Sultan Mahisawar are the main actors in the history that would be categorized by the experts as legends or myth. The defeat of the local Hindu King Parashuram at the

hand of Mahishawar is described in the story. The hi(story) has supernatural interventions unlike our established history writing. The line of narration does not follow the experts' version of cause and effect history and archaeology. More importantly, the conclusion of the story has two different versions. One version describes the defeat of the Hindu Raja as a consequence of the supernatural power of the Muslim Saint. Another version, describes the win as an effect of betrayal and treachery of the Muslim saint who threw a piece of beef in the palace of the king to cease the king's supernatural supremacy.

I have referred to the case of Mahasthan for different reasons. The example is one among the many about the existence of the different and oppositional narratives about the past pertaining of archaeological and heritage site at the contemporary period. It makes the varieties of history apparent. It shows us that history produced in fundamentally opposing principles and norms can exist, even when authority and dominance of one norm is evident in the urban space. Moreover, the versions including the experts' one is politically implicated. The 'mythical' history has signification differently to the identity of two religious groups – Hindu and Muslim. Respective versions represent the religious supremacy for each group. The dominant version, supported by the archaeological proof and objective support, is invoked by the experts, media and academia for asserting a nationally owned past. A past of glory, prosperity and communal harmony of the nation. A past that is owned by the dominant groups and desired by the powerful ideology of the state. The heritage of different period, this version claims, proves that the nation became civilized thousands years ago, that the ancestors established a prosperous urban centre many years back, that the Hindu, Buddhist and Muslim monuments and artifacts proves that from the very remote past the people of Bangladesh are living in communal harmony and peace. But, the hi(story) of the commons defies and delegitimizes these versions. The commons contest these versions in different ways.

At this point I want to call for a very recent event in Mahasthan. In November of 2010, construction of a multistoried building started by the Sultan Mahiswar Mazar Committee. Initially the local representatives of the Govt. Department of Archaeology failed to stop the construction on this prominent heritage site. It was stopped after High Court's rulings and intervention. The incident got huge media coverage, enquiry committees with experts were formed at different times, and the issue became international. I was among the few who protested from a different point. Off course the construction of a new building on the site was deplorable. However, the existence of a different narrative of the past and archaeological heritage and its oppositional relationship with the dominant history must be taken into account, I argued. This is not to say that we have to endorse the perception of the past and heritage in popular level. Rather, this was an event that overtly shows the undemocratic terrain of history writing and heritage making in Bangladesh. The hi(story) proves that the narrative of communal harmony and apolitical ideal of heritage are not valid. The commons are heterogeneous, their perceptions of the past and heritage are multiple and to protect the heritage in a democratic way we have to engage with the popular perceptions. We must not assume, as often we do, the commons have not perceptions of the past. They are unaware and ignorant about the past and heritage. This position also presupposes that they are not good citizens of the country as the believers in the dominant historical narratives are. They are uncivilized and they could be civilized

through education and awareness raising programmes. Interestingly, the prospect of these civilizing programmes opens the door for direct financial investments in the heritage sectors. Possibilities for the transforming the commons heritage and past into a heritage industry lurks on the horizons of the present.

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Few of us may remember the Guimet Museum debacle by the end of 2007 and the beginning of 2008. The proposed exhibition of various representative artefacts from Bangladesh in Guimet Museum in Paris raised severe critics and protests in the metropolitan urban space of Dhaka. Eventually the exhibition was cancelled after the lost of a Visnu sculpture from the international airport in Dhaka. There were disparities and conditions of inequality in the agreements between the Bangladeshi and French stakeholders. I want to recall that event as a marker of shift in the urban notion of heritage. The artifacts were selected and taken even from the display of different museums in Bangladesh including the hundred years old Varendra Society Museum, Rajshahi. It is interesting how 'heritage' became referent around which mobilization of a particular nationalist collective identity was invoked and circulated. In the claims of the protesters the artifacts became the embodiment and representative of the glorious national past of Bangladesh. It is the ever present past that justifies the aspirations and desires of the present. On the other side, the artifacts were selected for the exhibition in the orientalist logic that they represent the past glory of ancient Ganges delta. In that sense, the organizers themselves shared the same grammar of presenting the past of this region in terms of achievements. They were trying to construct a glorified national image of Bangladesh. Some people from the same urban space who tried to justify the exhibition claimed the need for uplifting the image of Bangladesh in international arena through the exhibition. The entire event becomes an example of democratic movement in reference to heritage. However, the democratic urge had its limitations and pitfall. Being completely urban in nature the mobilization could not address the fundamental aspects of a democratic past.

Hundreds of archaeological sites and artifacts are being destroyed, looted or smuggled in various parts of Bangladesh. Internal migrations, growth of settlements, expansion of agricultural lands along with the legal problems and institutional problems of the concerned Government Department of Archaeology, absence of funds for implementing the protection and preservation measures are few reasons among many for the destruction of archaeological heritage in Bangladesh. We have found during our last 10 years field work in northwestern part of Bangladesh that people who are destroying the archaeological sites are acting under the umbrella of present laws regarding land and property. Their actions, I have argued in several past cases, were conditioned by the structure of law, rather than their ignorance about a past.

Moreover, as it has been pointed to in reference to Mahasthan case, it could be argued in case of this part of Dinajpur-Joypurhat-Naogaon in the same way. Urban perception of the past rallies round experts' knowledge and nationalistic aspirations and validation of the politics of the nation-state. On the other hand, the popular perceptions are

performance of memorialization. Unlike the urban elitist experience of the heritage in museums, in air conditioned conference rooms or in the mobilizations, their everyday experience is shaped by the heritage and past. Their invocation of past is more the celebration of their living in the world through communitarian and religious identity. They address the archaeological heritage in terms of worshiping a mazar that is built on some ancient remains of temples or shrines. In a way, there is recognition of the conflicts in the common understanding of heritage. What is required is the encounter of the experts' perception and practice with the heterogeneous popular perception of the past.

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In July 2011, the foreign minister of Bangladesh claimed that Bangalees are the indigenous people of Bangladesh. The Bangali *Jaati* originated from the Archaeological place of Wari-Bateshwar 4000 years ago. The archaeological site of Wari-Bateshwar is much debated among the experts. Yet, the site has been popularized by media hypes with spectacular claims and interpretations. A heritage site when transformed into a spectacle, a celebration of civilized national identity may easily be manipulated by the nation-state. Indigenous Nations of Bangladesh are fighting for their constitutional recognition and rights. Their fights and struggles have their long history. What is completely new in the event is the use of heritage to legitimize the repression and dominance of a particular state ideology and policy making. It is important to look into the matter also in terms of civil-military-corporate capital in the Hill tracts and its possible nexus with the upcoming heritage industry in Bangladesh. Increasing amounts of investments in the heritage management enterprises could be a good indicator.

Past is always present. Politics of the past is part of our living in the modern world. The authority of the experts' and the dominance of particular majoritarian ideology can only be contested by engaging with the perceptions and practice of the past in the margin – the popular domain.

15 July 2012; 13, Bachelors' Quarter, Jahangirnagar University.